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CLUSTERING CITIES IN TURKEY WITH USING CLUSTER AND DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS FOR SOME DEMOGRAPHIC, EDUCATIONAL AND HEALTH INDICATORS

Filiz Ersöz, Nural Bekiroğlu, Şafak Aktaş, Pınar Günel, Yeliz Sevimli

Turkish Military Academy, Defence Sciences Institute, Department of Operational Research, Ankara, Marmara University, Medical School, Department of Biostatistics, Marmara University, Institute of Health Sciences, Department of Biostatistics, İstanbul,

fersoz@yahoo.com, nural@marmara.edu.tr,

ABSTRACT Objective; The aim of this study is to show that clustering 81 cities in Turkey with using indicators related with specific discipline gives more accurate and reliable results than using general and several indicators from each discipline. **Material and Methods;** In this study, selected demographic, educational and health indicators were used to cluster cities in Turkey. To decide the number of clusters for 81 cities, the hierarchical clustering method is used, and then non-hierarchical clustering (K-means) method is applied. To verify the validity of the results, they are compared with Discriminant Analysis. To analyze of the data, standard normal data by Z score transformation is used. **Results;** According to analysis of selected demographic, educational and health indicators; the hierarchical clustering result with dendogram, then non-hierarchical (K-means) clustering result and discriminant analysis result were given. Two summary tables; one is for each disciplines (Health; 4 indicators, Educational; 4 indicators, Demographic; 4 indicators) and the other one for all of the three disciplines with 12 Indicators were also given showing the Turkish cities in each cluster. **Conclusion;** Although number of clusters was found relatively small when 12 indicators are used to cluster 81 cities in Turkey, in this case the power of the analysis becomes poor because of fixed number of cities (sample size). However clustering 81 cities in Turkey according to specific purposes and disciplines with using very specific, reasonable and relatively less indicators, the results of cluster analysis becomes more reliable.

Key words: Discriminant Analysis, Cluster Analysis, Health, Education, Demographic, Indicators

ÖZET Amaç; Çalışmanın amacı, Türkiye'nin 81 ilinin kümelenmesinde, her bir disiplin için yapılan kümeleme analizinin, tüm disiplinlerin bir arada kullanılması ile yapılan kümeleme analizine göre daha kesin ve güvenilir sonuçlar olduğunu göstermektir. **Gereç ve Yöntemler;** Bu çalışmada, Türkiye'nin 81 ili için seçilen demografik, eğitim ve sağlık göstergeleri kullanılarak kümeleme analizi uygulanmıştır. Küme sayısına karar vermek için, aşamalı kümeleme yöntemi ve aşamalı olmayan kümeleme (K-Ortalamalar) yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Elde edilen sonuçların geçerli olduğunu doğrulamak amacıyla Diskriminant (Ayırma) Analizi uygulanarak karşılaştırma yapılmıştır. Verileri analiz etmek üzere her üç disiplin için hesaplanan dönüştürülmüş Z skorları kullanılmıştır. **Bulgular;** Seçilen demografik, eğitim ve sağlık göstergeleri için yapılan analizlere göre, dendogram ile aşamalı kümeleme, aşamalı olmayan kümeleme ve diskriminant analizi sonuçları verilmiştir. Ayrıca her kümede yer alan şehirleri gösteren, biri her disiplin için ayrı ayrı (sağlık; 4 gösterge, eğitim; 4 gösterge, demografik; 4 gösterge), diğeri 12 göstereyi içeren tüm disiplinler birlikte olmak üzere iki adet özet tablo verilmiştir. **Sonuç;** Türkiye'nin 81 ilinin kümeleme analizinde, 12 gösterge kullanıldığında küme sayısı oldukça küçük çıkmasına rağmen, bu durumda analizin gücü, illerin sabit sayısı nedeniyle zayıf olmuştur. Oysa özel disiplinler ve özgün amaçlar için yapılan Türkiye'deki 81 ilin kümeleme analizi sonuçları, özgün, makul ve görece olarak daha az gösterge kullanıldığından daha güvenilir olmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Diskriminant (Ayırma) Analizi, Kümeleme analizi, Sağlık, Eğitim, Demografik, Göstergeler

1. INTRODUCTION

Grouping techniques are often used in many fields such as sociology, health sciences, econometrics etc.

Exploratory procedures such as searching the data for a structure of 'natural' grouping or clustering are often quite helpful in understanding the complex nature of multivariate relationships. In this case, the selection of indicators become very important.

The aim of this study is to show that clustering 81 cities in Turkey with using indicators related with specific discipline gives more accurate and reliable results than using general and several indicators from each discipline.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this study for demographical clustering it is used; population increase rate, migration rate, fecundability rate, household size as indicators for 81 cities and for educational indicators; literate rate in Turkish population (2000) and number of student per teacher (2000), number of student per classroom (2006-2007) and the rate of graduates from universities (2006-2007) were selected for clustering 81 cities. For health indicators; number of specialized physician and practitioner, bed and hospital per 10000 population and rate of hospitalization between 2002-2004 were used to cluster.¹

To decide the number of clusters, the hierarchical clustering method is used, and then K-means (non-hierarchical) method is applied to cluster 81 cities in the clusters. To verify the validity of the results, the results are compared with Discriminant Analysis. SPSS 15.0 is used for the data analysis of this study. Also, we used standard normal data by Z score transformation for all the three disciplines. Z score transformation provides a way of standardizing data across a wide range of experiments and it allows also to compare different scales of data.

2.1. Cluster Analysis:

Cluster analysis is a kind of classification technique in that no assumptions are made concerning the number of groups or group structure. A cluster is a group of relatively homogeneous cases or observations. Grouping is done on the basis of similarities of distances (dissimilarities) using the variable values observed in each individual.²

More theoretically, the cluster analysis is the organization of a collection of patterns (usually represented as a vector of measurements, or a point in a multidimensional space) into clusters based on similarity. The clustering technique determines optimum partitions based on certain similarity and/or dissimilarity function that measures global error extent between data points and cluster centers in a feature space. In this regard, various algorithmic approaches are available including partitional algorithm, hierarchical clustering algorithm, graph-theoretic methods, fuzzy clustering algorithm, etc.^{3,4}

Hierarchical clustering techniques proceed by either a series of successive mergers or a series of successive divisions. Agglomerative hierarchical methods start with the individual objects. The results of agglomerative hierarchical method is displayed in the form of a two-dimensional diagram known as a dendrogram. The dendrogram illustrates the mergers or divisions which have been made at successive levels.⁵

Linkage methods are suitable for clustering. The average linkage is used in this study. In the average linkage method, groups are fused according to the average distance between pairs of members in the respective sets.²

K-means cluster method is the basic method for clustering. K Means Cluster Analysis is a non-hierarchical clustering method and this method is based on the assignment of the unit, in the classification of n units into k clusters, to a core cluster that is presented in the p dimensional space and reflects the profile of the majority of the units. In this method, means are the values of the k core points. K Means Cluster method only clusters the units and provides parameter estimates of the resulting clusters.³

2.2. Discriminant Analysis:

Discriminant Analysis is a multivariate technique concerned with separating distinct sets of observations and with allocating new observations to previously defined groups. A function that separates may sometimes serve as an allocator and conversely, an allocatory rule may suggest a discriminatory procedure. Discriminant analysis is rather exploratory in nature. As a separatory procedure, it is often employed on a one-time basis in order to investigate observed differences when causal relationships are not well understood. In this study, the discriminant analysis is used to sort observations into labeled classes and to verify the cluster analysis results.^{2,6,7,8} In this study, the discriminant analysis is used to sort observations into labeled classes and to verify the cluster analysis results.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Results of Demographic Indicators Clustering

3.1.1. Hierarchical Clustering Method

Hierarchical clustering technique proceeded by the average linkage method and the result is given in Fig.1.

Figure 1. Dendrogram with using Ward Method

3.1.2. Results of K-Means Clustering Method

K-Means Clustering result is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Cluster Membership

Case Number	Province	Cluster	Distance
1	Adana	3	10,162
2	Adiyaman	10	18,812
3	Afyon	3	7,595
4	Ađrı	10	5,827
5	Amasya	1	13,512
6	Ankara	6	12,625
7	Antalya	7	18,588
8	Artvin	8	6,622
9	Aydın	6	12,028
10	Balıkesir	6	11,403
11	Bilecik	9	9,297
12	Bingöl	1	10,087
13	Bitlis	3	7,818
14	Bolu	1	2,822
15	Burdur	3	13,598
16	Bursa	7	4,696
17	Çanakkale	6	16,770
18	Çankırı	3	4,990
19	Çorum	8	12,042
20	Denizli	6	7,653
21	Diyarbakır	10	11,495
22	Edirne	3	12,843
23	Elazığ	3	8,407
24	Erzincan	3	12,568
25	Erzurum	10	12,345
26	Eskişehir	6	7,528
27	Gaziantep	6	12,861
28	Giresun	3	8,189
29	Gümüşhane	3	8,283
30	Hakkari	3	20,218
31	Hatay	1	13,529
32	Isparta	6	16,961
33	İçel	6	9,580
34	İstanbul	7	3,202
35	İzmir	7	12,773
36	Kars	8	8,373
37	Kastamonu	1	14,308
38	Kayseri	3	12,019
39	Kırklareli	6	11,893
40	Kırşehir	1	5,105
41	Kocaeli	6	16,886
42	Konya	6	13,481
43	Kütahya	3	13,756
44	Malatya	3	9,293
45	Manisa	6	13,403
46	Kahraman	3	12,857
47	Mardin	10	16,148
48	Muğla	9	9,297
49	Muş	10	8,931
50	Nevşehir	3	9,941
51	Niğde	3	13,420
52	Ordu	1	8,149
53	Rize	3	9,815
54	Sakarya	3	7,907
55	Samsun	1	6,517
56	Siirt	8	16,541
57	Sinop	8	11,192
58	Sivas	1	10,934
59	Tekirdağ	5	,000
60	Tokat	10	8,490
61	Trabzon	3	9,264
62	Tunceli	4	,000
63	Şanlıurfa	10	19,400

64	Uşak	3	8,815
65	Van	10	12,978
66	Yozgat	10	11,182
67	Zonguldak	8	4,895
68	Aksaray	3	6,261
69	Bayburt	8	10,122
70	Karaman	3	2,954
71	Kırıkkal	1	11,563
72	Batman	10	9,159
73	Şırnak	6	16,291
74	Bartın	8	18,059
75	Ardahan	2	,000
76	İğdır	3	7,836
77	Yalova	6	11,529
78	Karabük	1	8,447
79	Kilis	1	13,019
80	Osmaniye	3	10,813
81	Düzce	6	6,604

Table 2. K Means Cluster Analysis (ANOVA)

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
Population Increase Rate,	1232,069	9	56,583	71	21,774	,000
Migration Rate	12038,407	9	87,355	71	137,810	,000
Fecudability Rate	4,022	9	1,134	71	3,545	,001
Household Size	4,546	9	,844	71	5,386	,000

According to the analysis variables are homogeneous in means of units. The significantly effective variables in the clustering of N=81 units are, in order of effectiveness, "Population Increase Rate" and "Migration Rate"(P<0,05). ANOVA result is given above Table 2.

Table 3. Number of Cases in each Cluster

Cluster	1	12,000
	2	1,000
	3	25,000
	4	1,000
	5	1,000
	6	16,000
	7	4,000
	8	8,000
	9	2,000
	10	11,000
Valid		81,000
Missing		171,000

Cases in each Cluster are given above Table 3.

3.1.3. Discriminant Analysis Results

Table 4. Test Results

Box's M		14,630
F	Approx.	,861
	df1	15
	df2	1958,422
	Sig.	,609

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

Discriminant Analysis Results are given above Table 4.

Table 5. Eigenvalues

Function	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Canonical Correlation
1	17,949	91,5	91,5	,973
2	1,666	8,5	100,0	,791

First 2 canonical discriminant functions were used in the analysis (Eigenvalue > 1). Eigenvalues Results are given above Table 5.

Table 6. Wilks' Lambda

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1 through 2	,020	290,265	18	,000
2	,375	72,574	8	,000

Wilks' Lambda Results are given above Table 6.

Table 7. Classification Results

		Predicted Group Membership											Total
		1,00	2,00	3,00	4,00	5,00	6,00	7,00	8,00	9,00	10,00		
Original	Count	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	
		0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		0	0	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	
		0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	16	
		0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	8	
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	11	
		%	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0
		,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	100,0	
		,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	100,0	

100,0% of original grouped cases correctly classified. Classification Results are given above Table 7.

10 clusters were found for demography, all indicators were statistically significant and according to discriminant analysis Wilk's Lambda was also extremely significant signifying that the characteristic of discrimination power of the function is high and it is verified also %100,0 of 81 cities were correctly classified.

3.2 Results of Educational Indicators Clustering

3.2.1. Hierarchical Clustering Method

Hierarchical clustering technique proceeded by the average linkage method and the result is given in Fig.2.

Dendrogram using Average Linkage (Between Groups)

Figure 2. Dendrogram with using Ward Method

3.2.2. K Means Clustering Analysis

K-Means Clustering result is given in Table 8.

Table 8. Cluster Membership

Case Number	ILLER	Cluster	Distance
1	Adana	1	1,165
2	Adiyaman	5	1,002
3	Afyon	3	,507
4	Ağrı	4	,693
5	Amasya	8	,328
6	Ankara	6	,000
7	Antalya	7	,668
8	Artvin	8	,574
9	Aydın	8	,433
10	Balıkesir	8	,586
11	Bilecik	8	,805
12	Bingöl	5	,777
13	Bitlis	5	,627
14	Bolu	8	,415
15	Burdur	8	,668
16	Bursa	1	1,405
17	Çanakkale	8	,542
18	Çankırı	3	,514
19	Çorum	3	,448
20	Denizli	8	,467
21	Diyarbakır	4	,818
22	Edirne	8	,485
23	Elazığ	1	,563
24	Erzincan	8	,484
25	Erzurum	1	,844
26	Eskişehir	7	,404
27	Gaziantep	5	1,801
28	Giresun	3	,203
29	Gümüşhane	3	,579
30	Hakkari	4	,324
31	Hatay	1	,617
32	Isparta	8	,635
33	İçel	1	,384
34	İstanbul	2	,000
35	İzmir	7	,893
36	Kars	3	1,104
37	Kastamonu	3	,426
38	Kayseri	1	,342
39	Kırklareli	8	,882
40	Kırşehir	3	,641
41	Kocaeli	1	,801
42	Konya	1	,542
43	Kütahya	3	,481
44	Malatya	1	,717
45	Manisa	3	,656
46	Kahraman	1	,896
47	Mardin	4	,496
48	Muğla	7	,996
49	Muş	4	1,031
50	Nevşehir	3	,384
51	Niğde	3	,305
52	Ordu	3	,659
53	Rize	3	,337
54	Sakarya	1	,839
55	Samsun	1	,637
56	Siirt	5	1,093
57	Sinop	3	,608
58	Sivas	3	,231
59	Tekirdağ	7	1,211
60	Tokat	3	,154
61	Trabzon	8	,488
62	Tunceli	8	1,090
63	Şanlıurfa	9	,000

64	Uşak	3	,390
65	Van	4	,360
66	Yozgat	3	,634
67	Zonguldak	8	,432
68	Aksaray	3	,305
69	Bayburt	3	,532
70	Karaman	3	,359
71	Kırıkkale	3	,497
72	Batman	4	,708
73	Şırnak	4	1,261
74	Bartın	3	,713
75	Ardahan	3	1,041
76	İğdır	5	,119
77	Yalova	7	,615
78	Karabük	8	,736
79	Kilis	3	1,138
80	Osmaniye	1	,637
81	Düzce	3	,540

Table 9. ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
Rate of graduates from universities	9,124	8	9,737E-02	72	93,706	,000
Literate rate in Turkish population	8,932	8	,119	72	75,294	,000
Number of student per classroom	8,412	8	,176	72	47,658	,000
Number of student per teacher)	8,520	8	,164	72	51,819	,000

ANOVA result is given above Table 9.

3.2.3. Discriminant Analysis

Table 10. Number of Cases in each Cluster

Cluster	1	14,000
	2	1,000
	3	27,000
	4	8,000
	5	6,000
	6	1,000
	7	6,000
	8	17,000
	9	1,000
Valid		81,000
Missing		171,000

Discriminant Analysis Results are given above Table 10.

Table 11. Test Results

Box's M		57,090
F	Approx.	2,029
	df1	24
	df2	2359,365
	Sig.	,002

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices of canonical discriminant functions. Test Results are given above Table 11.

Table 12. Eigenvalues

Function	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Canonical Correlation
1	17,792	74,5	74,5	,973
2	5,620	23,5	98,1	,921
3	,460	1,9	100,0	,561

First 3 canonical discriminant functions were used in the analysis. Eigenvalues Results are given above Table 12.

Table 13. Wilks' Lambda

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1 through 3	,006	384,931	24	,000
2 through 3	,103	167,857	14	,000
3	,685	27,989	6	,000

Wilks' Lambda Results are given above Table 13.

Table 14. Classification Results

		Predicted Group Membership										Total
		1,00	2,00	3,00	4,00	5,00	6,00	7,00	8,00	9,00		
Count	1,00	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	
	2,00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
	3,00	0	0	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	27	
	4,00	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	8	
	5,00	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	6	
	6,00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
	7,00	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	6	
	8,00	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	15	0	17	
	9,00	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	
%	1,00	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
	2,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0	
	3,00	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
	4,00	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
	5,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	
	6,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0	
	7,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0	
	8,00	5,9	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	5,9	88,2	,0	100,0	
	9,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	

93,8% of original grouped cases correctly classified. Classification Results are given above Table 14.

9 clusters were found for educational clustering, all indicators were statistically significant and according to discriminant analysis Wilk's Lambda was also extremely significant signifying that the characteristic of discrimination power of the function is high and it is also verified that %93,8 of 81 cities were correctly clustered.

3.3. Results of Health Indicators

3.3.1. Hierarchical Clustering Method

Hierarchical clustering technique proceeded by the average linkage method and the result is given in Fig.3.

Figure 3. Dendrogram with using Ward Method

3.3.2. K Means Analysis

K-Means Clustering result is given in Table 15.

Table 15. Cluster Membership

Case Number	ILLER	Cluster	Distance
1	Adana	1	,811
2	Adıyaman	2	,407
3	Afyon	3	,798
4	Ağrı	2	,626
5	Amasya	3	,608
6	Ankara	6	,873
7	Antalya	3	1,037
8	Artvin	8	,347
9	Aydın	3	,611
10	Balıkesi	3	,763
11	Bilecik	2	,777
12	Bingöl	1	1,042
13	Bitlis	2	,568
14	Bolu	4	1,119
15	Burdur	3	,882
16	Bursa	3	1,106
17	Çanakkal	3	,461
18	Çankırı	3	1,002
19	Çorum	3	1,263
20	Denizli	3	,339
21	Diyarbak	1	,980
22	Edirne	4	,523
23	Elazığ	4	,957
24	Erzincan	3	1,127
25	Erzurum	1	,998
26	Eskişehir	1	1,037
27	Gaziantep	7	,000
28	Giresun	3	,849
29	Gümüşhan	3	,722
30	Hakkari	2	,633
31	Hatay	2	,349
32	Isparta	4	1,217
33	İçel	3	1,094
34	İstanbul	5	,000
35	İzmir	6	,873
36	Kars	2	,858
37	Kastamon	8	,911
38	Kayseri	3	,672
39	Kırklare	3	,364
40	Kırşehir	3	,867
41	Kocaeli	3	,587
42	Konya	3	,940
43	Kütahya	1	,510
44	Malatya	1	,574
45	Manisa	1	,698

46	Kahraman	2	,719
47	Mardin	2	,991
48	Muğla	3	,881
49	Muş	3	1,258
50	Nevşehir	2	,714
51	Niğde	3	,831
52	Ordu	3	,651
53	Rize	3	,724
54	Sakarya	2	,534
55	Samsun	1	,945
56	Siirt	3	,697
57	Sinop	3	1,460
58	Sivas	1	1,234
59	Tekirdağ	3	,484
60	Tokat	3	,608
61	Trabzon	1	,495
62	Tunceli	3	,893
63	Şanlıurf	2	1,211
64	Uşak	3	,701
65	Van	3	1,066
66	Yozgat	3	,759
67	Zongulda	1	1,044
68	Aksaray	3	,894
69	Bayburt	1	1,044
70	Karaman	2	,832
71	Kırıkkal	1	,437
72	Batman	2	1,269
73	Şırnak	2	,952
74	Bartın	3	1,106
75	Ardahan	3	1,122
76	İğdır	2	,796
77	Yalova	3	,895
78	Karabük	8	1,072
79	Kilis	2	,852
80	Osmaniye	2	,171
81	Düzce	1	,712

Table 16. ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
NUMBER OF SPECIALIZED PHYSICIAN, PRACTITIONER	10,794	7	,061	73	177,483	,000
BED PER 10000 POPULATION	8,703	7	,261	73	33,293	,000
HOSPITAL PER 10000 POPULATION	9,046	7	,228	73	39,598	,000
RATE OF HOSPITALIZATION	8,805	7	,252	73	35,003	,000

ANOVA result is given above Table 16.

Table 17. Number of Cases in Each Cluster

Cluster	1	15,000
	2	18,000
	3	37,000
	4	4,000
	5	1,000
	6	2,000
	7	1,000
	8	3,000
Valid		81,000
Missing		171,000

Cases in each Cluster are given above Table 17.

3.3.3 Discriminant Analysis

Table 18. Test Results

Box's M		43,077
F	Approx.	1,927
	df1	20
	df2	6987,588
	Sig.	,008

Discriminant Analysis Results are given above Table 18.

Table 19. Eigenvalues

Function	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Canonical Correlation
1	18,917(a)	66,6	66,6	,975
2	5,249(a)	18,5	85,1	,917
3	3,789(a)	13,3	98,4	,889
4	,443(a)	1,6	100,0	,554

First 4 canonical discriminant functions were used in the analysis. Test Results are given above Table 19.

Table 20. Wilks' Lambda

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1 through 4	,001	500,045	28	,000
2 through 4	,023	278,667	18	,000
3 through 4	,145	143,068	10	,000
4	,693	27,161	4	,000

Wilks' Lambda Results are given above Table 20.

Table 21. Classification Results

			Predicted Group Membership							Total	
			1,00	2,00	3,00	4,00	5,00	6,00	7,00		8,00
Original	Count	1,00	13	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	15
		2,00	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	18
		3,00	1	0	36	0	0	0	0	0	37
		4,00	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	4
		5,00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
		6,00	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
		7,00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
		8,00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3
	%	1,00	86,7	,0	13,3	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0
		2,00	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0
		3,00	2,7	,0	97,3	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0
		4,00	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0
		5,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0
		6,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0
		7,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0
		8,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	100,0

93,8% of original grouped cases correctly classified. Classification Results are given above Table 21.

8 clusters were found for health, except the ratios of hospital all indicators were statistically significant and according to discriminant analysis Wilk's Lambda was also extremely significant that the characteristic of discrimination power of the function is high and it is also verified that %93,8 of 81 cities were correctly clustered.

3.4 Results of Three Disciplines (demographic, educational, health) Clustering.

3.4.1. Hierarchical Clustering Method

Hierarchical clustering technique proceeded by the average linkage method and the result is given in Fig.4.

Figure 4. Dendrogram with using Ward Method

3.4.2. K Means Analysis

K-Means Clustering result is given in Table 22.

Table 22. Cluster Membership

Case Number	ILLER	Cluster	Distance
1	Adana	2	2,419
2	Adıyaman	4	2,921
3	Afyon	1	,996
4	Ağrı	4	1,253
5	Amasya	1	1,065
6	Ankara	5	2,177
7	Antalya	2	3,084
8	Artvin	1	3,328
9	Aydın	2	1,209
10	Balıkesi	2	1,043
11	Bilecik	2	2,209
12	Bingöl	1	2,773
13	Bitlis	4	1,629
14	Bolu	1	2,841
15	Burdur	1	1,691
16	Bursa	2	2,055
17	Çanakkal	2	1,804
18	Çankırı	1	1,444
19	Çorum	1	1,217
20	Denizli	2	1,211
21	Diyarbak	4	1,936
22	Edirne	2	3,277
23	Elazığ	2	4,157
24	Erzincan	1	1,653
25	Erzurum	1	2,750
26	Eskişehir	2	1,825
27	Gaziantep	3	,000
28	Giresun	1	,984
29	Gümüşhan	1	1,519
30	Hakkari	4	1,874
31	Hatay	1	2,405
32	Isparta	2	3,447
33	İçel	2	1,553
34	İstanbul	5	2,177
35	İzmir	2	3,269
36	Kars	1	3,031
37	Kastamon	1	3,509
38	Kayseri	2	1,370
39	Kırklare	2	1,538
40	Kırşehir	1	1,234
41	Kocaeli	2	1,598
42	Konya	2	1,790
43	Kütahya	2	1,816
44	Malatya	2	2,059
45	Manisa	2	1,421

46	Kahraman	1	2,503
47	Mardin	4	1,581
48	Muğla	2	2,855
49	Muş	4	1,700
50	Nevşehir	1	1,605
51	Niğde	1	1,782
52	Ordu	1	1,042
53	Rize	1	1,059
54	Sakarya	1	1,936
55	Samsun	1	2,215
56	Siirt	4	2,289
57	Sinop	1	2,211
58	Sivas	1	1,911
59	Tekirdağ	2	2,794
60	Tokat	1	1,395
61	Trabzon	2	1,899
62	Tunceli	1	3,266
63	Şanlıurf	4	2,451
64	Uşak	1	1,504
65	Van	4	1,901
66	Yozgat	1	1,781
67	Zongulda	1	2,207
68	Aksaray	1	1,749
69	Bayburt	1	2,178
70	Karaman	1	1,650
71	Kırkkal	1	1,836
72	Batman	4	1,787
73	Şırnak	4	3,279
74	Bartın	1	2,133
75	Ardahan	1	3,021
76	Iğdır	4	2,471
77	Yalova	2	1,741
78	Karabük	1	2,316
79	Kilis	1	2,640
80	Osmaniye	1	2,571
81	Düzce	2	1,491

Table 23. ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
Specialized physician, practitioner	16,535	4	,182	76	90,655	,000
Bed per 10000 population	5,093	4	,785	76	6,492	,000
Hospital per 10000 population	11,927	4	,425	76	28,070	,000
Hospitalization	2,877	4	,901	76	3,192	,018
Fecudability Rate	15,696	4	,227	76	69,291	,000
Household size	15,534	4	,235	76	66,080	,000
Population Increase Rate	9,221	4	,567	76	16,253	,000
Migration Rate	10,571	4	,496	76	21,301	,000
Number of student per teacher	14,215	4	,304	76	46,682	,000
Number of student per classroom	12,362	4	,402	76	30,754	,000
Literate rate in Turkish population	16,663	4	,176	76	94,859	,000

The rate of graduates from universities	14,097	4	,311	76	45,377	,000
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ANOVA result is given above Table 23.

Table 24. Number of Cases in each Cluster

Cluster	1	39,000
	2	26,000
	3	1,000
	4	13,000
	5	2,000
Valid		81,000
Missing		171,000

Cases in each Cluster are given above Table 24.

3.4.3. Discriminant Analysis

Table 25. Test Results

Box's M		44,306
F	Approx.	1,951
	df1	20
	df2	4893,072
	Sig.	,007

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices of canonical discriminant functions. Discriminant Analysis Results are given above Table 25.

Table 26. Eigenvalues

1	5,437(a)	43,5	43,5	,919
2	4,247(a)	34,0	77,5	,900
3	1,805(a)	14,4	91,9	,802
4	1,010(a)	8,1	100,0	,709

First 4 canonical discriminant functions were used in the analysis. Eigenvalues Results are given above Table 26.

Table 27. Wilks' Lambda

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1 through 4	,005	354,344	24	,000
2 through 4	,034	228,653	15	,000
3 through 4	,177	116,755	8	,000
4	,497	47,134	3	,000

Wilks' Lambda Results are given above Table 27.

Table 28. Classification Results

		TMDISC	Predicted Group Membership					Total
			1,00	2,00	3,00	4,00	5,00	
Original	Count	1,00	0	0	0	0	1	1
		2,00	0	40	0	0	0	40
		3,00	0	0	4	0	0	4
		4,00	0	0	0	13	0	13
		5,00	0	3	0	1	12	16
		Ungrouped cases	0	1	0	0	6	7
	%	1,00	,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0	100,0
		2,00	,0	100,0	,0	,0	,0	100,0
		3,00	,0	,0	100,0	,0	,0	100,0
		4,00	,0	,0	,0	100,0	,0	100,0
		5,00	,0	18,8	,0	6,3	75,0	100,0
Ungrouped cases		,0	14,3	,0	,0	85,7	100,0	

93,2% of original grouped cases correctly classified. Classification Results are given above Table 28.

On the other hand, all of the 12 indicators belonging three disciplines were used to cluster cities in Turkey. 5 clusters were found more reasonable and according to discriminant analysis it is found that 93,2 % of original grouped cases correctly classified.

Table 29. Summary table for each disciplines (Health; 4 indicators, Educational; 4 indicators, Demographic; 4 indicators)

Results of K- Means Clustering Analysis										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
D e m o g r a p h i c I n d i c a t o r s	Amasya Bingöl Bolu Hatay Kastamonu Kırşehir Ordu Samsun Sivas Kırıkkale Karabük Kilis	Ardahan	Adana,Afyon Bitlis,Burdur Çankırı, Edirne Elazığ, Erzincan Giresun Gümüşhane Hakkari, Kayseri Kütahya, Malatya K.Maraş Nevşehir Niğde,Rize Sakarya Trabzon, Uşak Aksaray, Karaman İğdir, Osmaniye	Tunceli	Tekirdağ	Ankara, Aydın Balıkesir Çanakkale Denizli Eskişehir Gaziantep Isparta,İçel Kırklareli Kocaeli Konya Manisa Şırnak Yalova,Düzce	Antalya Bursa İstanbul İzmir	Artvin Çorum Kars Siirt Sinop Zonguldak Bayburt Bartın	Bilecik Muğla	Adıyaman Ağrı Diyarbakır Erzurum Mardin Muş Tokat Şanlıurfa Van Yozgat Batman
E d u c a t i o n a l I n d i c a t o r s	Adana Bursa Elazığ Erzurum Hatay İçel Kayseri Kocaeli Konya Malatya K.Maraş Sakarya Samsun Osmaniye	İstanbul	Afyon,Çankırı Çorum, Giresun Gümüşhane Kars, Kastamonu Kırşehir, Kütahya Manisa, Nevşehir Niğde,Ordu Rize,Sinop Sivas,Tokat, Uşak,Yozgat, Aksaray, Bayburt Karaman Kırıkkale Bartın, Ardahan Kilis,Düzce	Ağrı Diyarbakır Hakkari Mardin Muş Van Batman Şırnak	Adıyaman Bingöl Bitlis Gaziantep Siirt İğdir	Ankara	Antalya Eskişehir İzmir Muğla Tekirdağ Yalova	Amasya Artvin, Aydın Balıkesir Bilecik,Bolu Burdur Çanakkale Denizli, Edirne Erzincan Isparta Kırklare Trabzon Tunceli Zonguldak Karabük	Şanlıurfa	

H e a l t h I n d i c a t o r s	Adana Bingöl Diyarbakır Erzurum Eskişehir Kütahya Malatya Manisa Samsun Sivas Trabzon Zonguldak Bayburt Kırıkkale Düzce	Adıyaman Ağrı Bilecik Bitlis Hakkari Hatay Kars K.Maraş Mardin Nevşehir Sakarya Ş.Urfa Karaman Batman Şırnak Kilis Osmaniye	Afyon Amasya Antalya Aydın Balıkesir Burdur Bursa Çanakkale Çorum Denizli Giresun Gümüşhane İçel Kayseri Kırklareli Kırşehir Kocaeli Konya Muğla Muş Niğde Ordu Rize Siirt Sinop Tekirdağ Tokat Tunceli Uşak Van Yozgat Aksaray Bartın Ardahan Yalova	Bolu Edirne Elazığ Isparta	Istanbul	Ankara İzmir	Gaziantep	Artvin Kastamonu Karabük		
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Summary table for each disciplines, the results are given above Table 29.

Table 30. Summary table of all the three Disciplines (12 Indicators)

Results of K- Means Clustering Analysis						
	1	2	3	4	5	
Demographic, educational and health Indicators	Afyon Amasya, Artvin, Bingöl, Bolu, Burdur, Çankırı, Çorum, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırşehir, K.Maraş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Tokat, Tunceli, Uşak, Yozgat, Aksaray, Bayburt, Kırıkkale, Bartın, Karaman, Ardahan, Karabük, Kilis, Osmaniye	Adana, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bursa, Çanakkale, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Eskişehir, Isparta, İçel, İzmir, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Muğla, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Yalova, Düzce	Gaziantep	Adıyaman, Ağrı, Bitlis, Diyarbakır, Muş, Siirt, Ş.Urfa, Van, Batman, Şırnak, Iğdır	Ankara, İstanbul	

Summary of all the three Disciplines and the results are given above Table 30.

4. CONCLUSION

Although number of clusters was found relatively small when 12 indicators are used to cluster 81 cities in Turkey. In this case the power of the analysis becomes poor because of fixed number of cities (sample size). However clustering 81 cities in Turkey according to specific purposes and disciplines with using very specific, reasonable and relatively less indicators, the results of cluster analysis becomes more reliable.

There is no consensus on the cities belonging to the clusters, even it is analyzed for each discipline and 12 indicators. It is hard to determine similar cities in Turkey whatever the

research area. We think that there will be great changes in health area in recent years because of increasing number of private hospitals and the general health security system.

Therefore, we think also that when the 'clustering of cities' is questioned, clustering them according to the research purpose gives more accurate and reasonable results reflecting the reality.

Another remarkable result is that the developed cities such as İstanbul, İzmir and Ankara are seemed to be different comparing with the other cities in Turkey according to clustering with demographic, educational, health indicators separately and also with all indicators together. This result shows that economically developed cities are taking place generally in the same cluster whatever the research area.

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